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QUALIFYING EXAMINATION

Question:

1. Discuss the ‘**Main Advances in Post-Harvest Technologies for Coffee that Contribute to the Improvement of Grain/Seed Quality and Beverage**’¹

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Advancements in post-harvest technologies that contribute to the quality of coffee beverages have been occurring in recent years due to the increasing market demand for high-quality coffees with acceptable levels of mycotoxins. However, these advancements primarily involve adopting existing technologies rather than developing new post-harvest techniques. For instance, the wet processing method, currently a trend in the pursuit of beverage quality, has been reported since around 1730 in the East Indies (Tosello, 1957). However, although it has been known and utilized in countries where the dry period of the year is not well defined, such as Colombia, its adoption in Brazil has only grown in the last two decades due to the demand for high-quality coffees initiated by Illycaffè.

The progress in the development and, most importantly, the adoption of post-harvest technologies favorable to beverage quality is intertwined with consumer market demands for quality and the remuneration provided to coffee growers. Despite the knowledge of producing high-quality coffee for over a century, adopting post-harvest technologies incurs financial costs only viable if the purchasing market pays the difference for quality. In this regard, consumer demand for quality coffees drives the improvement of beverage quality within the producer market.

Findings from Junqueira and Garcia (2011) indicate that, among inferior (*rio zona, rio*) and superior (gourmet) beverages, Brazilian consumers prefer coffee of lower standards. According to the authors, Brazilian consumers prefer a more rustic, bitter, and less acidic coffee, demonstrating that consumer preference is not directly linked to product quality but their consumption habits. As changing consumption habits takes time, the concern for improving beverage quality has primarily been among producers targeting the domestic market. However, in the same study, the authors also observed that 80% of respondents would be willing to pay more for a high-quality coffee, provided they could recognize some quality differentials, such as a good beverage classification or a seal guaranteeing better quality. This indicates that the market for high-quality coffees holds promise if consumers can identify the best coffees through descriptions on the packaging. The advancement and adoption of post-harvest techniques are essential to enhance beverage quality and ensure that the final product is free from contaminants, especially mycotoxins such as ochratoxin A.

The quality of coffee beverages is influenced by numerous factors related to seed formation and post-harvest practices. However, the foundation for obtaining high-quality drinks lies in the specific quality of each bean that forms the lot for consumption. The

utmost quality of each bean is typically achieved when the fruit reaches the stage of physiological maturity of the seed. In the coffee fruit, this stage coincides with the red coloration of the exocarp, which characterizes the "Cherry II" ripening stage. Harvesting at this stage makes it difficult for subsequent techniques to improve the specific quality of each bean. However, considering a group of beans, the beverage quality can be enhanced during post-harvest by eliminating defective beans and preserving the quality of regular beans. In this context, separating defective beans is easy, but the main challenge lies in maintaining the quality of regular beans until consumption, particularly during the drying process. Drying theoretically seems easy, but in practice, the large volumes to be dried within a short period make the operation challenging, especially in regions with high humidity during harvesting.

Difficulties in coffee post-harvest practices begin with fruit harvesting, particularly in Brazil, where the adopted method is complete stripping, harvesting immature, ripe, and overripe fruits together. This variation in ripening stages results in significant differences in the anatomy, chemical composition, moisture content, and potential beverage quality of the fruits and seeds. For post-harvest to be efficient and preserve the potential grain quality, specific treatments must be applied to each ripening stage. Thus, immediately after harvesting, separating the fruits according to the treatments is necessary, typically forming at least three groups based on the ripening stage: dried fruits, green fruits, and cherries.

Technologies to perform this separation have existed for many years; however, they require specific equipment usually unavailable to small-scale farmers due to the associated costs. In addition to the equipment costs, the separation process generates residues that need to be adequately treated before being released into the environment, further complicating the adoption of the technology.

The wet processing method allows for the separation of fruits based on their ripening stage. However, in Brazil, the dry processing method, which produces what is known as natural coffee, is still widely adopted. This processing method involves drying the coffee in its natural form and preserving all parts of the fruit until the milling stage. In this method, typically used by producers without adequate infrastructure, coffee with different ripening degrees is processed together, with only the floaters being separated. Although it is a traditional method widely used in tropical regions with a well-defined dry season, it has the lowest potential for obtaining high-quality coffees in terms of post-harvest practices.

For this reason, the following paragraphs will discuss post-harvest technologies related to wet processing. The subsequent topics will address critical points in coffee post-harvest practices that represent advancements in improving the quality of grains/seeds and beverage.

Wet processing

The first records of wet processing date back to around 1730 in the East Indies (Tosello, 1957), indicating that it is not an innovative processing method. However, its adoption has been limited to countries in equatorial regions with no predominant dry season. Wet processing differs from dry processing in that the former involves separating green fruits from ripe fruits during the pulping stage of cherry fruits, which is not the case in dry processing.

In the past, wet processing was restricted to humid regions where drying coffee with the cherry intact did not occur quickly enough to prevent fermentation and subsequent decline in grain quality. However, in recent years, due to the market demand for high-quality coffees, wet processing has been adopted in Brazil as a strategy for producing superior beverage coffees. In addition to reducing the possibility of undesirable fermentations in the beans, wet processing allows for separating green beans from cherries, as the harvest is done by complete stripping, enhancing the production of superior beverages.

In countries like Colombia, the advantage of wet processing is primarily related to the drying time, as selective harvesting is carried out due to the large number of flowering events that occur in the coffee plantations of that country. The separation of fruits according to their ripening stage aims to preserve the intrinsic organoleptic characteristics of each stage, enabling the production of beverages that cater to different market niches.

Wet processing can be conducted in three distinct ways: mechanically removing the skin and mucilage through biological fermentation, resulting in pulped coffee, which is the most widely used method in wet processing worldwide; mechanically removing the skin and part of the adhering mucilage, resulting in peeled cherry coffee, known as CD, which is the most common wet processing method in Brazil; or mechanically removing the skin and mucilage, producing demucilated coffee (Borém, 2008).

In wet processing, separating fruits according to their ripening stage and the pulping of cherry fruits facilitate faster drying, avoiding undesirable fermentations and

producing high-quality beverages. However, Silva (2003) reports that selecting and pulping cherry coffees alone does not guarantee high-quality beverages. Through a survey conducted on 32 properties in the South of Minas Gerais, the author identified that even with pulping, 75% of the samples had a hard beverage. Although no samples with defective or Rio beverage were found, pulping alone did not guarantee the production of soft and strictly soft beverages, demonstrating that various other factors, such as adjustments in the pulper, dryer, and the inherent quality of the harvested beans significantly influenced the process.

Despite not guaranteeing the quality of the beans, the increasing adoption of wet processing in Brazil represents a significant advancement in post-harvest technology aiming to improve the quality of beans and beverages. By allowing the pulping of green, cherry, and overripe fruits, wet processing facilitates the drying of beans, preventing the development of yeast and fungi that deteriorate the flavor and aroma of coffee. In addition to easing drying, wet processing allows the composition of lots with only physiologically ripe fruits, producing extremely high-quality beverages.

Post-harvest of green fruits: Promising advancements in post-harvest techniques have been achieved in the processing of green fruits. With the growing adoption of wet processing in Brazil, it has become possible to enhance the drying process of green fruits (Borém et al., 2006a), improving the final beverage quality obtained from immature coffee. The improvement in the beverage quality derived from green fruits, although it may not reach the quality of cherry fruits, represents a significant premium for coffee growers, signifying an important advancement in coffee post-harvest practices.

According to Borém (2008), the cherry and green coffee lots are optimized by adjusting the pulper to remove the counterweight that forces pulping. In this way, only physiologically ripe fruits tend to be pulped, minimizing the possibility of an immature fruit negatively affecting the cherry coffee lot. According to Puerta-Quintero (2000), the presence of just 2.5% of green fruits in the harvest would be sufficient to result in the sensory analysis disqualifying 30% of the cups due to unpleasant flavors. Removing the counterweight, in addition to benefiting the cherry coffee lot, enriches the green fruit lot by including more fruits in the green-cane and cherry stages. After separation, Borém (2008) recommends that the lot composed of green fruits remain stacked for approximately 20 hours, after which it should be pulped, this time keeping the counterweights halfway on the arms that regulate the pulping pressure. However, in a recent study, Nobre et al. (2011) observed that this resting period for green coffee is

unnecessary, and the pulping of immature fruits can be carried out immediately after pulping the ripe fruits without compromising the quality. According to Borém et al. (2004), by increasing the pulping pressure, it is possible to pulp around 41% of the green coffee after the stacking period, even though in the green lot, cherry coffee represents less than 10% of the total pulp. After processing and drying, this lot of green coffee presents an average of only 2.8% of PVA (black, green, sour defects) and hard/green beverage (Borém, 2008).

Borém et al. (2005) compared lots of pulped cherry coffee, pulped green coffee, and cherry + green coffee processed via dry processing regarding various characteristics related to beverage quality. They observed that pulped green coffee showed similar quality to that obtained for cherry + green coffee but was significantly inferior to the quality of pulped cherry coffee. Despite being a lot of green coffee, the pulping operation causes the detachment of the spermoderm usually adhered to the endosperm, and since the endosperm does not have the coloration that characterizes the green defect, there is a reduction in the percentage of PVA (black, green, sour defects). In addition to the improvement in the coffee type, the beverage has been classified as hard/green, with no rio characteristic in the pulped green lots. Due to the reduction in the discount for green coffee, through its separation and pulping, the economic viability of acquiring equipment and infrastructure for pulping cherry coffee increases, resulting in an overall increase in the production of high-quality coffees with added value (Borém, 2008).

Drying Temperature

After the incidence of fungi causing undesirable fermentations in coffee, high drying temperatures and speeds have been considered the main factors contributing to the loss of coffee quality during post-harvest. Drying coffee, compared to other products, is more challenging to execute because the harvested fruits have a moisture content of around 60% wet basis (w.b.), and the mucilage has a high sugar content, promoting product deterioration within a few hours after harvest.

With the adoption of the wet processing method, high-quality coffee undergoes drying with only the endocarp or with the endocarp and part of the mucilage (mesocarp). In both cases, it is referred to as parchment drying. This differs from the drying of natural coffee due to the difference in fruit exposure to the environment. This difference occurs because the parchment-covered seeds lack the exocarp to protect them from mechanical stress, solar radiation, or temperature fluctuations.

According to Borém (2008), proper drying is achieved when water is removed slowly, preserving the integrity of the grain's interior and preventing fermentation. However, the challenge lies in the need to dry large volumes of coffee within a short period. Drying at lower rates would require a larger drying area or more time in mechanical dryers, which would increase costs per sack by necessitating additional infrastructure and labor in post-harvest operations. In an effort to reduce costs, coffee growers are using high temperatures that lead to a loss in the final quality of the coffee lot, particularly affecting those with the potential to produce high-quality beverages.

During the drying process, depending on the temperature and drying rates used, chemical, physical, and physiological transformations can occur in the beans. In the case of inappropriate temperatures, these transformations tend to cause disorganization or alteration of the selectivity of the cell membranes (Saath et al., 2010; Borém et al., 2008a).

With the disorganization and rupture of cell membranes, there is leakage of oil and other cellular components, which are then exposed to oxygen and compromise the quality of coffee. Seeds with damaged cell membranes leach a greater amount of solutes, resulting in higher electrical conductivity and potassium leaching, leading to a loss of beverage quality (Borém et al., 2008b), as well as germination potential and vigor (Carvalho and Nakagawa, 2000).

Borém et al. (2006b) evaluated parchment coffee beans dried at 40°C and 60°C and observed, through histochemical studies, that in the beans dried at 40°C, the compartmentalization of oil bodies was maintained after drying, and they were evenly distributed throughout the inner perimeter of the plasma membrane. In contrast, in the endosperm of beans dried at 60°C, fusion of the oil bodies occurred, forming large droplets in the intercellular space, indicating the rupture of the plasma membrane and oil vesicles.

Saath et al. (2010), evaluating the effects of temperatures of 40°C and 60°C on grain mass during coffee drying using scanning electron microscopy of the endosperm, confirmed that a temperature of 40°C is suitable for drying the grains up to their storage moisture content. However, contrary to common observations, they reported that a temperature of 60°C could be used without causing damage to cell integrity as long as it is applied until a moisture content of 40% w.b. for pulped coffee and 30% w.b. for natural coffee. However, further studies are needed to better understand and confirm these results before making recommendations, as other parameters related to beverage quality still need to be evaluated.

In seed production, Harrington (1972) states that the higher the seed moisture content, the lower the temperature should be used for drying. In line with this, Borém et al. (2008b) recommend that the temperature in the horizontal dryer during pre-drying (drying up to 30% w.b.) should not exceed 30°C, and after the mid-drying stage, it can be increased to 40°C for parchment coffee and 45°C for natural coffee.

The inadequate temperature during drying, especially in mechanical dryers, can not only alter the beverage but also cause changes in the grain color, leading to unevenly colored products, which adversely affects the appearance of the lot and reduces its market value (Borém et al., 2008b; Menchú, 1967).

Based on research findings in recent years, it is generally recommended that pre-drying be preferably done on the patio, as the initial phase of drying involves rapid moisture loss. If a mechanical dryer is used, when the coffee reaches 30% moisture content, the volumetric contraction will be sufficient for the upper part of the drying chamber to be empty, causing loss of hot air and reducing the efficiency of the process. After the mid-drying stage, the use of a mechanical dryer becomes more desirable. In this case, the drying temperature of the coffee should be monitored, with the thermometer probe reaching at least 50% of the radius of the horizontal dryer, ensuring that the temperature within the grain mass does not exceed 40°C for parchment coffee, 45°C for natural coffee, and 35°C for green fruits (Borém et al., 2008b).

Partial drying of cherry coffee

Partial drying of cherry coffee refers to the interruption of the drying process when the beans still have a high moisture content, followed by a resting period before resuming drying. The objective is to reduce the effective drying time and standardize the moisture content of the beans. The drying efficiency increases due to water loss that occurs during the initial resting period when the beans are still warm and the redistribution of moisture within the beans during the rest period.

In addition to improving drying efficiency, resting periods for the beans can represent a significant advancement in coffee post-harvest practices aimed at improving grain/seed quality and beverage quality. Begazo (1979), who studied the drying of pulped coffee with intermittent resting periods, obtained a product with a smooth beverage, bluish coloration, and uniform moisture content, which are desirable characteristics in coffee.

Isquierdo et al. (2011) conducted a study on peeled cherry coffee using a horizontal dryer. They evaluated the interruption of drying at moisture levels of 16%, 20%, and 24%, combined with resting periods of two, six, and twelve days. They observed that when drying was interrupted at a moisture content of 24%, regardless of the resting period duration, the damage to the membrane system was lower compared to other treatments, including the standard treatment represented by continuous drying until the storage moisture content.

According to the authors, although no differences were detected among the treatments in terms of total sugars, reducing sugars, non-reducing sugars, grain coloration, and sensory analysis of the beverage, it is possible that after a storage period, the greater preservation of the membrane system could have a beneficial effect on the sensory quality of the beverage.

Partial drying, if confirmed not to compromise coffee quality, can be employed during specific stages of harvesting, particularly in high-yield years when more efficient use of coffee drying infrastructure is necessary. With this option, if drying is the only limiting factor, it will be possible to harvest a larger quantity of coffee within a timeframe compatible with the optimal fruit maturation point, thus promoting a final improvement in beverage quality.

From the topics discussed, it is evident that the main post-harvest technologies for enhancing coffee beverage quality are theoretically simple and follow the same principles as the production of high-quality seeds. In a simplified manner, the foundation of post-harvest practices for producing quality coffee beans/seeds lies in harvesting fruits whose seeds have reached physiological maturity, peeling without causing damage to the seeds, and drying at optimal temperatures and rates. However, despite being well-known technologies that have only been improved in recent years, their adoption is still not common among the majority of coffee growers due to financial limitations and a lack of knowledge about beneficial existing technologies. Given the increasing global demand for high-quality coffees, it is increasingly necessary to advance by innovating and improving post-harvest technologies and enhancing their dissemination among producers. This can be achieved by providing technical training and supporting the financing of the necessary infrastructure.

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